

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: BRAZIL

Limnology of Drylands – SIL Working Group Report

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Currently, the elucidation of the consequences of climate change and human impacts on drylands is a priority, considering the vulnerability of these zones. Accordingly in 2016, we created the International Network on Limnology of Drylands (INLD - www.inld.pro.br) in Areia (Paraíba, Brazil), aiming to expand our knowledge on aquatic ecosystems in dryland zones by focusing on biodiversity, climate change effects, and local multiple stressors. A few months after its foundation, the INLD was formalized through the creation of the International Society of Limnology (SIL) Working Group “Limnology of Drylands”. Since its creation, INLD has been established in regions such as Europe, Africa, Asia, Oceania, South and North America. The projects and actions developed in these regions are based on the space-for-time approach, gathering information about multiple stressors in

Fig. 1 Congress of the Network of Environmental Studies of Portuguese Speaking Countries (Angola, Africa)

aquatic ecosystems (e.g., eutrophication, salinization, climate change) from local and global perspectives.

Regarding the activities performed around the world, in 2019 some actions were carried out in Brazil, Africa, and Australia. Firstly, INLD was present at the Congress of the Network of Environmental Studies of Portuguese Speaking Countries, held in Angola (Africa), which allowed the consolidation of relevant partnerships between Portugal, Cape Verde, and Brazil (Fig. 1). In the same year, fieldwork was performed across the dryland zones of Australia, by Professors Brian Timms and Luciana Barbosa, aiming to assess the biodiversity distribution in Australian rockpools (gnammas) (Fig. 2). Also, in 2019 INLD held a workshop entitled *Knowledge gaps and analysis tools in temporary ecosystems* at the “XVII Brazilian Congress of Limnology and the 2nd Ibero-American Congress of Limnology”. Among the main outcomes of this workshop, we highlight the creation of the INLD subproject “Scientometric and meta-analysis studies in global dryland freshwater ecosystems”, currently being developed.

In 2020, a special issue of *Inland Waters* (<https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/tinw20/10/4?nav=tocList>), dedicated to “Limnology of Drylands”, was edited by Guest Editor Prof. Luciana Barbosa (INLD President and Chairperson) and supported by Editor-in-Chief Dr David Hamilton. This issue included 9 articles about the biodiversity of aquatic environments from different continents (Barbosa *et al.*, 2020a; Carvalho *et al.* 2020; de Farias *et al.* 2020; Hulot *et al.*, 2020; Ilhéu *et al.*, 2020; Lanfranco *et al.*, 2020; Morant *et al.*, 2020; Silva *et al.*, 2020; Zadereev *et al.*, 2020) and an editorial paper (Barbosa *et al.*, 2020b) that presented INLD, its objectives, mission, as well as a theoretical vision of dryland zones worldwide. Emphasis was given to the updated INLD objectives: i) to assess the current state of biological diversity in dryland aquatic ecosystems; ii) to evaluate the multiple environmental stressors acting in drylands; iii) to develop predictive models to estimate the effects of global changes on drylands.

The emergence of the COVID pandemic in 2020, promoted changes in the international scenario, imposing new meeting formats to continue ongoing activities. Thus, the Working Group Meetings were held online, enabling a much wider participation of members and colleagues from different countries. Among the special sessions in 2021, the first one was held in the 10th International Shallow Lakes Conference under the title “Ecology and energy flow in tropical temporary ecosystems”. This meeting was coordinated by INLD and the Ecology Laboratory from the Federal University of Rio

Fig. 2 Professors Brian Timms and Luciana Barbosa in Australian gnammas

de Janeiro, Brazil, with presentations emphasising aquatic community ecology, as well as, energy and matter flow, which expanded the understanding of the functioning of temporary ecosystems across drylands regions.

In the 35th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2021), INLD held a special session called “Ecology, management and conservation of temporary water bodies”, coordinated by INLD, the International Society for Salt Lakes Research - ISSLR, and the Ecology Laboratory from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. This session featured presentations from Brazil, South Korea, China, and Spain. Additionally, the official Working Group Meeting had a special focus on the actions developed between 2019 and 2020, as well as a proposal for planning future actions, including the establishment of common field and laboratory protocols to be implemented by members in all countries. Common protocols

Fig. 3 Official Meeting of Working Group “Limnology of Drylands” in the 35th Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL2021).

will greatly facilitate data sharing and analyses. Colleagues from Brazil, Spain, Portugal, Mexico, Egypt, Ecuador, Greece, Hungary, India, among others, were present (Fig. 3). Recently, INLD participated in the Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network meeting (GLEON), discussing the relevance of international cooperation in climate change scenarios to mitigate environmental problems in lakes worldwide.

Nowadays, the main projects being developed by INLD are: i) “Scientometric and meta-analysis studies in global dryland freshwater ecosystems” aiming to understand and fill research gaps in dryland areas around the world; ii) “Rockpools (and temporary ecosystems) in world drylands: trophic interactions and the relationship between diversity and ecosystem stability”; iii) “Galapagos program: Iconic Galapagos aquatic ecosystems as a climate change hot-spot?”.

The future challenges for INLD will include understanding the synergistic effects of climate change and local human impacts on aquatic ecosystems. Accordingly, current alterations in the water balance in dryland zones are promoting increases of extreme droughts on broad scales, reducing hydroperiods and impacting water quality in zones with great scarcity of this important resource. Thus, more research is needed in dryland zones, especially in underrepresented countries, which might significantly contribute to the understanding of global impacts on dryland aquatic biodiversity.

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In memoriam of Dr. Brij Gopal
Member of INLD Executive committee

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